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PROJECT PROPOSAL: MONKAYO SLAUGHTERHOUSE IMPROVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The expansion of the municipal slaughterhouse is one of the top priorities for the Monkayo local government, which will be undertaken in response to the pressing need for slaughtering services and poultry dressing facilities in the developing local economy. In 2019, the country was affected by the African Swine Flu (ASF). As a result, local government units, pig farmer organizations, veterinary groups, the commercial sector, and academic institutions collaborated to reduce the number of cases. This is also one of the centerpieces of the effort to improve the slaughterhouse services to be able to sustain the safety control of the meat products. With this objective and desirable outcome, the Monkayo municipal administration is working to upgrade the existing meat facilities and ensure they meet the National Meat Inspection Services' standards. The researchers conducted a technical assessment of the project through a feasibility study to evaluate the improvement of the service capacity of the proposed facility. The project is expected to deliver sustainable, ecologically safe, and high-quality products to the municipality, the region, and the entire country.

Keywords: slaughterhouse; African Swine Flu; meat facility; meat processing

PROJECT RATIONALE

The expansion of the municipal slaughterhouse is one of the top priorities for the Monkayo local government, which will be undertaken in response to the pressing need for slaughtering services and poultry dressing facilities in the developing local economy. In 2019, the country was affected by the African Swine Flu (ASF). As a result, local government units, pig farmer organizations, veterinary groups, the commercial sector, and academic institutions collaborated to reduce the number of cases. This is also one of the centerpieces of the effort to improve the slaughterhouse services to be able to sustain the safety control of the meat products. With this objective and desirable outcome, the Monkayo municipal administration will work to upgrade the existing meat facilities and ensure to meet the National Meat Inspection Services' standards.

The Municipality of Monkayo currently has policies in place for Municipal Slaughterhouse/Abattoir and Corral Fees, which include rules and regulations governing the operation, such as obtaining a permit to slaughter, the nature and imposition of fees, and maintaining the municipal abattoir's cleanliness and sanitation. Moreover, in accordance to R.A. 9296 where the local government units shall regulate among others, meat inspection, meat transport and post-abattoir control.

The project is expected to deliver a sustainable, ecologically safe, and high-quality products to the municipality, the region, and the entire country. Specifically, the activities are expected from the project include,

- a. Local ordinance requiring all food businesses to serve only inspected meat in order to provide consumers with access to clean and safe meat products that satisfy "AA" standards.
- b. Operation of the Municipal Slaughterhouse compliant with environmental laws and regulation, ensuring continued compliance with national standards
- c. TESDA accreditation for butchery, slaughtering, and meat processing that would increase farm productivity and livelihood opportunities for the people of Monkayo.

- d. Lastly, the slaughterhouse may be used as a research and laboratory facility that will give an educational opportunity for MonCAST, the local agriculture office's academic partner with its BAT program.

METHODOLOGY

This study will employ a quantitative research approach. Specifically, the technical assessment of this project will be through a feasibility study. The outcome of the study was shared with relevant departments for consultation with all stakeholders to ensure the credibility and reliability of the information.

TECHNICAL ASSESSMENT OF THE PROJECT

Market Study

The slaughterhouse expansion project aims to expand its service capacity to address the growing demand for quality and safe meat to consume around the identified neighboring municipalities such as; Montevista, Compostela, and Trento. A market study has been administered in each market areas to analyze the projected demand for slaughterhouse services against its target service capacity.

Historical Demand – Monkayo Market

Shown in the table 1 below is the historical demand of Monkayo market, there are two (2) identified market classifications which are the public market meat vendors and individuals, analyzed for the past three years. Figures are in number of heads.

Table 1. Historical Demand of Slaughterhouse Services - Monkayo

	2018	2019	2020
Meat Vendors	4,641	4,819	4,841
Individuals	10,829	11,244	11,210
Total Historical Demand - Monkayo	15,470	16,063	16,051

Projected Demand – Monkayo Market

Shown in the table 2 is the projected demand of Monkayo market. Based on the analysis on its historical demand a 2.10% average increase was determined to project its demand for the next three (3) years. Figures are in number of heads.

Table 2. Projected Demand of Slaughterhouse Services - Monkayo

	Base Demand	Average Increase Percentage	Projected Demand
Year 1	16,051	2.10%	16,388
Year 2	16,388	2.10%	16,732
Year 3	16,732	2.10%	17,083

Current Capacity

Slaughterhouse current capacity is averaging in to 20 heads per day with its 2:00 AM to 5:00AM regular operation schedule. See details in table 3 below. Figures are in number of heads.

Table 3. Current Service Capacity

	Daily	Monthly	Annually
Slaughterhouse – Current	20	600	7,200

Target Capacity

The slaughterhouse expansion project will triple its current service capacity based on the additional resources from its facilities to manpower, which will address the growing demand of its services. A comparison of current and targeted service capacity of slaughterhouse is shown in table 4. Figures are in number of heads.

Table 4. Target Service Capacity

	Current Capacity	Target Capacity
Slaughterhouse Service Capacity	7,200	21,600

Projected Demand – Target Capacity Analysis

Target Service Capacity of slaughterhouse is analyzed against the Projected Demand of Monkayo market which resulted to an excess capacity that can accommodate the demand of target markets from nearby municipalities; Montevista, Compostela, and Trento. Figures are in number of heads.

Table 5. Projected Demand – Target Capacity Analysis of Slaughterhouse

	Target Service Capacity	Projected Demand- Monkayo Market	Excess Capacity*
Year 1	21,600	16,388	5,212
Year 2	21,600	16,732	4,868
Year 3	21,600	17,083	4,517

Projected Demand – Outside Monkayo

Projected demand of the target nearby municipalities are shown on table 6. Projected demand was computed by analyzing their respective historical demand based on the 15 kg per capita meat consumption. Details of historical demand computation for identified markets outside Monkayo is reflected in the appendices. Figures are in number of heads.

Table 6. Projected Demand – Outside Monkayo Market

Target Market - Nearby Municipalities	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Montevista	21,600	16,388	5,212
Compostela	21,600	16,732	4,868
Trento	21,600	17,083	4,517
Total Projected Demand-Outside Monkayo	14,849	15,429	16,021

Intended Market Areas of Slaughterhouse

Shown in the map below is the intended market areas which are marked with red flags.

Figure 1. Map – Intended Market Areas

Market Share

The figures have shown the market share of Slaughterhouse after expansion from the target nearby market from Montevista, Compostela, and Trento. The excess capacity can accommodate the three (3) year projected demand outside the municipality with 35%, 32%, and 28% respectively.

Table 7. Market Share – Outside Monkayo Market

	Excess Capacity (Head)	Projected Demand Outside Monkayo (Head)	Market Share (%)
Year 1	5,212	14,849	35%
Year 2	4,868	15,429	32%
Year 3	4,517	16,021	28%

PROPOSED SLAUGHTER FEES

Proposed rate will remain the same from its existing rate based on Section 5G.08 of Municipal Tax Ordinance No. 2018-01 (The Revised Municipal Revenue Code of 2018).

Hogs

Table 8. Current and Proposed Rate for Slaughterhouse Services - Hogs

Slaughterhouse Services	Current Rate	Proposed Rate
Ante-mortem	Php 15.00	Php 15.00
Post-mortem	Php 15.00	Php 50.00
Corral Fee	Php 15.00	Php 15.00

Cattle

Table 9. Current and Proposed Rate for Slaughterhouse Services - Cattle

Slaughterhouse Services	Current Rate	Proposed Rate
Ante-mortem	Php 20.00	Php 20.00
Post-mortem	Php 100.00	Php 100.00
Corral Fee	Php 75.00	Php 75.00

Goat

Table 10. Current and Proposed Rate for Slaughterhouse Services - Goat

Slaughterhouse Services	Current Rate	Proposed Rate
Ante-mortem	Php 15.00	Php 15.00
Post-mortem	Php 50.00	Php 50.00
Corral Fee	Php 15.00	Php 15.00

Projected Receipts from Slaughterhouse Operations

Projected Receipts are computed using projected demand of respective livestock multiplied with its corresponding proposed rate of slaughterhouse services. Detailed computation is shown in the appendices.

Table 11. Total Projected Receipts from Slaughterhouse Operation

	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Hogs	Php 1,728,000	Php 1,728,000	Php 1,728,000
Cattle	Php 28,080	Php 28,665	Php 29,250
Goat	Php 19,200	Php 19,600	Php 20,080
Total Projected Receipts	Php 1,775,280	Php 1,776,265	Php 1,777,330

The current receipts of slaughterhouse have increased in to 100% through analyzing the trend of its past three-year receipts of operation. In average, the recorded gross receipts of the slaughterhouse operation is Php 519, 283.00 which will be doubled if the improvement project will be implemented in to an average of Php 1,042,058; considering the increase of its service capacity due to facilities improvement, additional staffing, and expansion of intended market areas.

PROJECT COST

Presented on the data below is the capital expenditure in carrying out the expansion of the slaughterhouse. An engineer’s perspective of the proposed building is shown in appendices including schedule of specifications for the fixtures and auxiliary equipment.

Table 12. Slaughterhouse Improvement Project Cost

Building	Php	12,995,000.00
Fixtures		
Hog Line		942,340.00
Cattle Line		1,702,025.00
Equipment		
Auxiliary Equipment		604,462.50
Total Project Cost	Php	16,243,827.50
Government Grant - DANMIS	Php	8,121,913.75
LGU of Monkayo - Equity	Php	8,121,913.75

As per Joint DA-DILG-DBM Memorandum Circular No. 1 Series of 2006 Section VI Article 1 that the National Meat Inspection Services (NMIS) thru Local Government Units (LGUs) Meat Establishment Improvement Program (MEIP) shall shoulder the 50% of total project cost of the meat establishment. In the case of Monkayo Slaughterhouse Improvement Project the NMIS shall cover **Php 8,121,913.75** of the Total Project Cost of **Php 16,243,827.50** and the half amount will be shouldered by the Local Government Unit of Monkayo amounting to **Php 8,121,913.75**

PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION SCHEDULE

The improvement project of the slaughterhouse aimed to commence its implementation in Year 2022. Shown in table 13 is the schedule of quarterly implementation.

Table 13. Project Implementation Schedule

Activities	Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4
Pre-project Operation	✓			
Construction of Infrastructure	✓			
Procurement and Installation of Equip-	✓			
Organizing and Staffing	✓			
Training and Seminars	✓			
Enactment of Pertinent Municipal Ordi-		✓		
Operation and Maintenance			✓	✓

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the technical assessment, the fulfillment of the project will increase the service capacity of the facility, which could address the entire demand of Monkayo. Furthermore, the facility will still have excess service capacity, which could address the demand of the neighboring municipalities. Hence, the researchers suggest that the Local Government Unit of Monkayo should take the opportunity to expand and improve the existing slaughterhouse facility by contributing 50% of the total project cost. This will enhance the quality and safety of the meat products consumed by the Monkayoans and residents of nearby municipalities. Also, when the project is finished, the improved slaughterhouse will have better services and a bigger market area.

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